

Predicting the Water Removal of Refractory Castables – The Key Milestones to Further Understand and Optimize Monolithic Drying

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Abstract:

The drying of monolithic refractories remains a significant entry barrier for many potential markets and equipment that could benefit from their unique features such as automated application, higher installation rates and lack of expansion joints. Although the promise of using numerical models to predict drying behavior and to optimize this lengthy process - while avoiding explosive spalling - is not new and has been explored since the early 1990s, most industrial drying processes still rely on semi-empirical approaches. These methods result in extended maintenance shutdowns, profit losses, and unnecessary CO₂ emissions. Bridging the gap between reliable and practical numerical tools and real industry applications requires an in-depth understanding of the mechanisms during water removal and an appropriate selection of assumptions that can accurately capture the observed behavior. This is a long-term endeavor, and immediate economic and environmental improvements cannot wait, especially in the current challenging context. Thus, the present work addresses the major milestones that could drive the decision-making on simulating drying and illustrates several insights and guidelines obtained from the currently existing, albeit imperfect, models. Key findings include the confirmation of the moisture-clogging phenomenon, the role of thermomechanical stresses in explosive spalling, and the impact of weepholes on drying efficiency. Thermomechanical simulation results are also presented to investigate potential hypotheses for the mechanisms driving the permeability increase in fiber-containing castables. These insights provide practical guidance for optimizing drying processes today, with the potential to reduce downtime, minimize emissions, and improve overall efficiency in refractory applications, while also laying the ground for improved models that will eventually lead to optimized and safe heat-up curves.

1. Introduction

Hydraulic bonded refractory castables can be categorized as a partially saturated porous media [1]. In this category of materials, their pores comprise various contents of fluids depending on the position and time. When studying the drying of monolithics, the fluids involved are liquid water, dry gas (a mixture comprising nitrogen, oxygen, carbon dioxide) and water vapor [2].

In this context, when considered more broadly, drying refers to the process in which a liquid is extracted from a partially or fully saturated porous media by means of imposing gradients of pressure, concentration and temperature. This phenomenon involves both heat and mass transport [3].

For refractory castables, besides the water removal related to the traditional concept of drying, it is also critical to consider the decomposition of the hydrates - which are the results of the reaction between the added water and the binder system [3, 4, 5, 6]. This decomposition reaction must be completed before the material is heated to its final operation temperature, and thus, it is also a process that is considered as a part of the drying [4].

However, as the castables compositions became more closely packed to improve its mechanical performance and corrosion resistance [3], the pressurization of the vapor resulting from evaporation and dehydration reactions became the limiting to the water removal rate, as the higher pressures act both as a greater driving force for water removal and also as a mechanical load that can lead to catastrophic failure [1, 3, 5 6].

A quick assessment of how drying is usually carried out in the industry shows that this process often involves three distinct actors with differing and sometimes conflicting priorities [7]: first there is the end-user, focused on rapidly restoring full production capacity with the least amount of costs; there is also the refractory supplier, concerned with ensuring the material's service life and mitigating liability for potential failures; and finally there usually is the figure of a contractor, responsible for managing the heating process under challenging industrial conditions, trying to adhere strictly to predefined protocols to minimize responsibility in case of accidents. These competing interests can result in a "tripartite impasse" [8], where uncertainty obstructs traceability and diffuses the accountability among the involved parties – sometimes even intentionally.

In an ideal future scenario, which should – and probably will – be eventually reached, numerical simulations will become a crucial tool benefitting all stakeholders. First, they will enable the engineering of new compositions based on how its properties will impact the water withdrawal process and the likelihood of facing explosive spalling. Second, they will aid the contractors to have tailored heat-up procedures that account for the characteristics and limitations of a given set of material, boundary conditions, application site, etc. optimizing the drying time, while simultaneously ensuring safety. Finally, they would decrease the downtime for the end-user's by mitigating long overconservative heat-up curves, which are typically applied to minimize the risk of explosive spalling but often extend production halts [3, 5, 9].

This desired hypothetical situation requires a numerical model that captures the main mechanisms of heat and mass transport in the material [1, 6, 10], as well as reproducing the resulting strains and stresses of such processes. Achieving such a level of accuracy demands a thorough understanding of the phenomena that takes place during drying, as well as precise measurements of the necessary properties [11], and most importantly, how they evolve during the drying process itself.

There are several difficulties to this, such as the fact that drying process is highly dynamic, with the castable material surpassing multiple changes on its microstructure during the water removal process, such as removal of capillary water films, shrinkage of the solid skeleton, conversion among the less stable phases to the ones more stable and the dehydration itself [4]. On the other hand, most of the characterization techniques available at the laboratory scale are based on stationary conditions such as permeability measurements and thermal conductivity [12, 13].

Another complicating factor is the wider use of global methods that measure the evolution of a single property of the whole sample – such as the mass evolution on thermogravimetry [3, 5, 14] – and which neglect the local aspects of heat and mass transfer. Often, these analyses are also done on samples at the laboratory scale, and only recent the size effect on the drying behavior started to be investigated [15].

Additionally, there is a lack of experimental techniques capable of capturing material properties under the required conditions. For instance, to the best of the authors knowledge, no existing thermal conductivity measurement equipment allows for controlled relative humidity at higher temperatures, and there is a need for high temperature permeameters capable of providing accurate measurement of the in-situ evolution of permeability. Methods and equipment capable of determining sorption isotherms – which define the amount of free, evaporable water in a porous medium at a given pressure and temperature – are also cumbersome [16], or inexistant for measurements at temperature higher than 80°C.

Finally, it should also be considered the significant computational power that is required to simulate the key processes during drying, which take place across multiple scales, from the structural dimensions on the order of meters to molecular interactions occurring at the Ångström scale.

Although recently progress has been made on these aspects – and more resources should still be invested to surpass them – in the last decade, the strategy of the authors have been to also explore and study how the current models, with their current capabilities and known limitations could be used to gather important insights that could already be useful to reduce the drying times and increase the process safety, while the most accurate computational tools are still under development.

Thus, the current work aims to present a review of the key milestones in the use of numerical simulations for the investigation of refractory castables drying. In the next sections, a brief introduction is presented for each topic, followed by a short description on the methods applied and results that illustrates and summarizes the advances achieved at each stage.

2. Milestone 1: Selecting an Appropriate Model for Drying Simulations

When considering the literature, several different modelling approaches exist to simulate the water removal process were developed over time [1]. These models rely on different assumptions and may differ in both complexity and user-friendliness. Figure 1 presents an overview of the primary categories used to classify these numerical methods.

Fig. 1: Overview of numerical model classifications and categories for drying analysis [17].

One way to classify the different possible modelling strategies for predicting drying behavior is according to the physics involved, which can be purely thermal, thermohygro, or thermohygro-mechanical. A thermal model predicts only temperature distribution and cannot reliably estimate the steam pressure buildup inside the castable. Although Antoine’s law can provide a theoretical maximum vapor pressure, it does not account for vapor escaping the material, which reduces pressure [1].

Thermohygro models consider both heat transfer and mass transport, enabling predictions of water distribution and pressure inside the material. Thermohygro-mechanical models go further by incorporating the mechanical effects, assessing the stresses induced by the thermal and vapor pressure related strains [1].

Models can also be classified by their coupling approach. Fully coupled models allow mutual interactions between the different physical process, whereas one-way coupled models impose effects in a “single direction” (e.g., considering pressure effects on stress but not stress effects on permeability itself) [1].

Another distinction is the number of phases considered. Single-phase models simplify the mass transfer analysis by assuming that only a single fluid phase that represents all the gases and liquids inside the material are being transported [18]. Such single-phase models may produce unrealistic relative humidity predictions [19]. On the other hand, multiphase models account for the mass transport of all the different phases inside the partially saturated porous media and even though they are more accurate, they also require numerous material properties that are difficult, or even impossible to measure at the conditions found during the drying process.

Finally, the models can differ in the scales that are involved in the simulation. Most studies use homogenized models, which average the material properties and ignore microstructural heterogeneities. In contrast, mesoscopic models account for these variations, offering a more detailed representation at the expense of higher computational costs and overall complexity of the model [1, 18].

For a detailed presentation of these models, readers are referred to previous work from the authors [1, 11]. The models are based on conservation equations from Classical Irreversible Thermodynamics (CIT) [1], which state that the time derivative of a quantity, plus the divergence of its flux, equals any sources or sinks in the region of interest, as shown by Equation 1:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\text{density}) + \nabla \cdot (\text{flux}) = \text{source} \quad (1)$$

Regarding the mass conservation, three models were implemented and compared, they are: i) the Single-phase (SP) model, which represents moisture as a combined liquid and vapor phase; (ii) Multiphase model without capillary pressure (NCP), which distinguishes liquid and gas phases but neglects capillary effects; and (iii) Multiphase model with capillary pressure (CCP) that includes capillary pressure effects at the liquid-gas interface.

The different assumptions from such models impact the thermal energy conservation equation, as mass flux affects the heat transfer. In the SP model, mass flux follows Darcy's law, while NCP and CCP models also account for gas-phase diffusion. Additionally, NCP considers adsorbed water movement.

The resulting system of partial differential equations is solved numerically using the finite element method (FEM). The computational implementation in this work is based on the FEniCS platform [20], an open-source framework using C++ and Python. The results are visualized with Python.

The case selected for analysis represents a Portland cement concrete cylindrical sample (with diameter of 30 and 60 mm in height) being dried by radiant heater. During the drying, neutron tomography was performed, with the resulting attenuation intensity being directly proportional to the water content. Such results were compared with the predictions of the three evaluated models, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Evolution of the water content distribution calculated with the different models and obtained using neutron tomography [21].

All the simulations effectively captured the drying front propagation velocity, defined by the abrupt change in water content, in agreement with neutron tomography data. However, some differences between the models were identified. The CCP model exhibited more pronounced lateral drying, likely due to capillary effects, a behavior not observed in the NCP and SP models. In contrast, the SP model showed intensified drying at the sample's top and bottom regions. Despite these distinctions, all models qualitatively represented the moisture distribution, which is a direct product of the pressurization inside the material. Thus, depending on the required level of precision, a simplified model may be a viable option for estimating pressure values with reasonable accuracy.

3. Milestone 2: The Existence of the Moisture Clog Phenomenon

One important aspect revealed by the neutron tomography tests was the existence of the moisture clog, a phenomenon where there is a local reduction of the material permeability thanks to the condensation of liquid water at positions closer to the cold surface of the castable [22].

The current section highlights how the accumulation of water at the innermost positions of the sample is also predicted in the numerical simulations. The case selected for analysis represents a CAC-bonded castable sample (5 wt.% CAC, with the complete composition given in [9]) with the dimensions and boundary conditions representing those from the in-situ drying analysis using neutron tomography as described in [22]. The model considered is the SP model and the results are compared with the neutron attenuation intensity measured in the tomography tests. The results are shown in Fig. 2. Two different conditions were considered: with a ceramic enclosure around the sample, restricting the radial mass flux, and without it.

The results of water distribution in the sample with casing shown in Fig. 3 a) revealed that the drying front velocity is closely reproduced by the model, considering both the principal front moving from the top to the bottom surface, as well as the secondary front that develops on the cold surface. The moisture accumulation however was smaller in the numerical results.

For the sample without the casing, Fig. 3 b), the drying front velocity was well captured by the model and even its blunt shape was reproduced. Again, the water accumulation was underestimated in the simulations.

It should be noticed that the sorption isotherm (i.e., the state function that defines the physically adsorbed water inside the material) for the 5CAC composition was not measured and the boundary conditions could be better adjusted to fit the experiments. In these results, the effect of the water accumulation on the permeability was not considered. This, however, is critical for accurate predictions, especially in larger and more complex geometries, and could result in closer magnitudes between the experimental moisture accumulation and the numerical results.

Fig. 3: Comparison of water distribution evolution predicted by the SP model with experimental results from neutron tomography for a sample a) without or b) with a ceramic casing.

The key conclusion from this analysis is that the simplest SP model can effectively capture the primary characteristics of the drying process, even in two different conditions (with and without the casing).

4. Milestone 3: Weep-hole Effects on Drying and Design Discussions

The same SP model was also used to understand the effects of adding weepholes at the outer steel shell of refractory castables lining [23]. The geometry selected for this study is the section of a wall from a steel ladle, represented by a prismatic mesh, considering the following thicknesses: 200 mm for the working layer, 50 mm for the permanent layer, and 34 mm for the insulating one, as presented in Fig. 3.

The boundary conditions used enforce symmetry of heat and mass transfer on the side planes of the ladle sample. Specifically, the larger sides of the ladle, measuring 284 mm x 100 mm in Fig. 4, exhibit symmetry. In the current case, the weep holes are arranged in a square mesh pattern with 200 mm between the weep holes centers. The temperature at the hot face of the working layer was imposed through a Dirichlet boundary condition.

Fig. 4: Numerical mesh and layer materials representing the weep hole. Units are in meters [23].

The cold surface is subject to cooling by convection and radiation, and mass transfer is only possible at the 1/4th of a circle representing the weep, or at the hot face itself. The remainder of the cold face, representing the steel shell was assumed impermeable.

The simulations began at 25°C, and the temperature at the hot face was increased at a rate of 100°C/h until it reached 825°C. Two cases were considered, one where the region representing the weep hole is permeable, and one where it is impermeable.

Fig. 5. shows the maximum pressure evolution for both cases. During the initial stage of pressurization, between 0h and 3.7h, there are no differences between the scenarios, as the drying front is – at such instants – restricted to regions closer to the hot face. This leads to only a small moisture flow towards the cold surface. As the moisture accumulates at the innermost positions of the sample, the effect of permeable weep holes is noticeable, with a difference over 15MPa between the conditions with and without holes. Such a pronounced pressurization suggests the development of a high-pressure vapor region within the lining, thanks to the moisture accumulation.

Fig. 5: Maximum pressure evolution for the conditions with and without weep holes [23].

The distribution of pressure and water content for the sample comprising weepholes are presented in Fig 6 a) and b), respectively. It is observed that the pressurization at the drying front pushes the free water content to the deeper positions of the working layer, and that the moisture velocity vectors are orientated towards the weep hole, serving as an escape route for the water, reaching velocities as high as 10mm/s.

Fig. 6: Cross sections and cold face pressure and free water distribution in the sample comprising weep hole [23].

These results demonstrate that weep holes are critical in the dynamics of water removal, enabling the escaping of water at the cold face, reducing the moisture accumulation in the core of the lining, and the pressure levels inside the material. This approach can be further utilized to optimize the ladle shell design in a way that maximizes the drying rates and mitigates the risk of explosive spalling, while maintaining the structural integrity of the steel ladle.

5. Milestone 4: The Role of Thermomechanical Stresses on Explosive Spalling

Up until this point, the previous milestones did not include the analysis of the mechanical behavior of the refractory lining during the drying process. The present section discusses the role of the thermomechanical stresses on the explosive spalling behavior.

Using the same single-phase thermohygro model as a basis, the momentum balance equation is coupled to the mass transfer balance through Biot's theory of consolidation [2], providing the "hydraulic" strain, ϵ_{hyd} , shown in Eq. 2, and the thermomechanical strain, ϵ_{th} , depicted in Eq. 3.

$$\epsilon_{hyd} = \frac{b}{K} p_g \mathbf{I} \quad (2)$$

where b is the Biot coefficient, K , is the bulk modulus, p_g the gas pressure and \mathbf{I} the second-order identity tensor.

$$\epsilon_{th} = \alpha \Delta T \mathbf{I} \quad (3)$$

where α is the thermal expansion coefficient and ΔT the temperature variation in comparison to the reference state.

Combining such strains with the elastic one and using the phase-field model framework for simulating the fracture mechanics, extreme scenarios where either the hydraulic or the thermomechanical are neglected by assuming $b = 0$ or $\alpha = 0$, respectively, could be simulated for a plane wall geometry. A third case where it was assumed $b = 1$ and the thermal expansion coefficient of calcium aluminate cement castable was also analyzed. The boundary conditions for these analyses are summarized in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7: a) Dimensions of the plane wall section analyzed and b) summary of the boundary conditions.

The results of temperature, pressure and free water distributions are the same, as the proposed methodology considers a one-way coupling (i.e. the damage effect on the permeability, thermal conductivity and other thermohygro properties are disregarded), and are shown in Fig. 8 for the moment the crack initiation was predicted by the model considering both the hydraulic and thermomechanical strains.

Fig. 8: Spatial distributions of a) temperature, b) pressure and c) free water content at the moment of crack initiation predicted by the model comprising both the hydraulic and thermomechanical strains.

At this moment, the hot face reached around 225°C, whereas the maximum pressure reached 1MPa, with the drying front penetrating roughly 1/4th of the total lining thickness. Fig. 9 presents the maximum principal stresses and phase-field variable at the moment of failure for the three considered cases.

Fig. 9: Maximum principal stresses and the damage variable, ϕ , distribution at the moment the crack initiated when a) the thermomechanical strains were neglected, b) the hydraulic strains were disregarded, and c) when both were considered.

The thermomechanical stresses primarily governed the resulting explosive spalling behavior, as indicated by the similarity in displacement magnitudes and stress distributions observed in the tests where the hydraulic strains were neglected and the full model (Fig. 9 b and Fig. 9 c).

In contrast, when thermal expansion was disregarded, Fig. 9 a), the mechanical response was predominantly influenced by the pressurization zone, as expected, with the maximum principal stress exhibiting a compressive peak around the pressurization zone, aligning with the moisture pressure distribution shown in Fig. 8 b).

These findings align with energetic analyses, which emphasize the dominant role of thermal stresses in explosive spalling [1, 3, 5]. Furthermore, they reinforce the necessity of additional mechanisms beyond vapor pressurization to account for the observed explosive spalling behavior [5, 24].

6. Milestone 5: Assessment of the Microcracking Hypothesis for Polymeric Fibers Permeability Enhancing Mechanism

The final example of how computational simulations can be used to better understand the drying of refractory castables considers a preliminary assessment of the microcracking hypothesis for permeability enhancement mechanism of polymeric fibers.

This hypothesis states the experimentally observed increase of castable permeability in castables comprising fibers originates by radial cracks that are developed at the interface between the fiber and matrix during heating of the sample, thanks to the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between such phases [25].

Although Zhang et al. have identified cracks in *post-mortem* Portland cement concrete samples using scanning electron microscopy [25], no direct proof exists of this phenomenon, and the observed failures could be related to the cooling of the bodies, the sample preparation, or other reasons. Thus, the current section aims to provide a preliminary analysis on the feasibility of this hypothesis. An analytical thermomechanical model based on linear elasticity and isotropic materials developed by Zago et al. [26] was used with the properties obtained by the literature and from Zhang's work. The model outputs the radial displacement, from which the radial and tangential stresses can be obtained, as shown in Fig. 10. Three polymers are simulated: linear low-

density polyethylene (LLDPE), ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) and polypropylene (PP).

Fig. 10: Existing stresses around a polymeric fiber and description of the analytical problem for predicting the radial displacement. Adapted from [26].

Fig. 11 shows the tangential stress distribution along the radial direction. It can be seen that compressive stresses are present inside the fiber, as the matrix hinders its expansion. At the interface between the phases, the maximum tensile tangential stress is observed, with the sample comprising polypropylene showing stresses at roughly 220 MPa for a 150°C instant temperature increase.

Fig. 11: Tangential stresses as a function of radial position for LLDPE, UHMWPE and PP.

It should be noticed that these estimates are highly dependent on the properties considered for each phase described. Additionally, the assumption of perfectly linear elastic solids is not accurate specially around the fibers melting point, where viscoelasticity becomes critical in defining the stresses at these materials. Nonetheless, the substantial values of tangential stresses calculated even for the sample with smallest thermal expansion coefficient (UHMWPE), around 20 MPa, suggests that the possibility of microcracking taking place cannot be disregarded without further studies on this matter.

7. Conclusions and Future Prospects

The current work presented a review of the key milestones in the use of numerical simulations for the investigation of refractory castables drying. It was shown that the simplest single-phase model was able to capture the primary characteristics of the drying process, even in two different conditions (with and without the casing). This model was also able to reproduce the

moisture clog phenomenon, which is a critical aspect of the drying process. With such tool, the effects of adding weepholes at the outer steel shell of refractory castables lining were investigated. The results showed that these holes are critical in the dynamics of water removal, enabling the escaping of water at the cold face, reducing the moisture accumulation in the core of the lining, and the pressure levels inside the material. This approach can be further utilized to optimize the ladle shell design in a way that maximizes the drying rates and mitigates the risk of explosive spalling, while maintaining the structural integrity of the steel ladle.

The role of the thermomechanical stresses on the explosive spalling behavior was also discussed. The results showed that the thermomechanical stresses primarily governed the resulting explosive spalling behavior, as indicated by the similarity in displacement magnitudes and stress distributions observed in the tests where the hydraulic strains were neglected and the full model. In contrast, when thermal expansion was disregarded, the mechanical response was predominantly influenced by the pressurization zone, as expected, with the maximum principal stress exhibiting a compressive peak around the pressurization zone, aligning with the moisture pressure distribution.

Finally, a preliminary assessment of the microcracking hypothesis for permeability enhancement mechanism of polymeric fibers was presented, revealing large tangential stresses even for the sample with the smallest thermal expansion coefficient (UHMWPE), suggesting that this mechanism should be further investigated.

The results presented in this work demonstrate that numerical simulations have great potential in advancing the understanding of refractory castables drying, and that, even before fulfilling their complete potential, critical insights and general guidelines can already be obtained.

8. References

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